

Towards a Generic Curriculum for Educational Robotics in STEM: From Scientific Concepts to Technologies and Powerful Ideas

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Abstract

This paper and its corresponding poster present a “work in progress” concept for the visualization of 19 activity plans, into a generic curriculum map for teaching STEM concepts through constructionist robotics activities. There are six educational paths that represent potential use cases and these have been validated through 148 educational robotics workshops implemented with children between the ages of 7 and 18 in six European countries.

Keywords

educational robotics, curricula, robotics, workshop, science, technology, engineering, mathematics, learning, STEM

Introduction

Many children lose their natural curiosity for how things function and interrelate to each other along the way into their lives as young adults. The ER4STEM project aims to turn curious young children into young adults passionate about science and technology with a hands-on use case: robotics. In this poster we present our effort to develop a generic curriculum for robotics using a bottom-up approach: i.e. analysing several activity plans produced as part of the project. Our analysis follows different educational paths aiming to construct a curriculum that addresses the different facets of educational robotics: a) powerful ideas; b) scientific concepts and skills; c) technologies and engineering; d) mathematics. The result of this analysis is presented in the form of a 'metro map' showing how an educator could navigate through the educational robotics activity plans taking each of these educational paths.

We embarked on this effort understanding that a curriculum is a complex concept, which ends up being a matter of profound philosophical discussion, as it yet revolves around the notion of knowledge and notably, of what is of importance to be learned for the individual within the context of the society, in which they function (Bers, 2003). However, in our case, instead of following a top-down approach and looking at what should be learned in terms of educational robotics, we followed a bottom-up approach. Consequently, we analyse how we can identify teaching and learning elements, which are connected to the nature of educational robotics: i.e. constructionist technology, multidisciplinary domain, subject matter and a domain for contextualized learning of other subject matters.

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A Generic Curriculum for Applying Educational Robotics in STEM-Related Education

Among the core goals of the project is to deliver a generic educational robotics curriculum. It aims to facilitate usability of the project's products by a broader community of relevant stakeholders such as, but not limited to, teachers, researchers and 3rd sector organisations.

Assuming the general definition of curriculum being a general plan for educational activities, Adams and Adams (2003) define a curriculum as everything that goes in the learners' life such as planned and not planned interaction of pupils with educational objectives, instructional content, materials and resources used and materials and resources not used, the sequence of courses, objective, standards and interpersonal relationships.

In order to accomplish the project objectives and to research the domain of using robotics in education, we organise educational robotics workshops. The activities developed follow a learning design instrument "Activity Plan Template", which aims at raising teachers' awareness of the key characteristics of educational robotics implemented in constructionist ways (Yiannoutsou et al 2017).

Taking into account the above mentioned curriculum definition and the experience gained so far, we decided to use a bottom-up approach for organising the 19 Activity Plans as adoptable generic curriculum paths organised around Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics domains and further complemented by arts, business and 21st century skills.

The activity plans were designed, implemented and validated through 148 educational robotics workshops with more than 3500 students implemented in Austria, Bulgaria, Greece, Malta, Ireland and the UK, over two years. However, due to time constraints, the entire curricula paths, consisting of an educational sequence of activity plans as a single entity were not implemented. Therefore, we consider the curricula on the level of educational paths of a generic nature by design and they will need to be further adapted to meet context specific desired learning outcomes, specific objectives and classroom needs.

The Six Educational Paths Visualised as a “Metro Map”

With this generic educational robotics curriculum, we want to assist teachers in adapting a learning path, consisting of a set of educational robotics workshops or single activities within the workshops activity plans, that are suitable for their context, students, specific objectives and prior knowledge.

The six educational paths built around the STEM domains, are based on the following use cases:

1. An educator aims to teach **technology and engineering with Lego Mindstorms robots**. This is a typical use case of using robots for education
2. An educator aims to teach concepts of **science, technology and engineering while demonstrating various technology platforms** such as Arduino, Beebots, Hedgehog, LEGO Mindstorms and LEGO WeDo **as well as a vast plethora of** programming languages C++, Python, LEGO Mindstorms Programming, Scratch or SNAP.
3. An educator aims to cover all STEM domains, **Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, while also developing creativity and business skills among the students**.
4. An educator aims to teach concepts in **science, technology and engineering through “white box”** platforms such as:” Arduino, Hedgehog, LEGO WeDo with a stronger focus on electronics and widely used industrial programming languages such as C++ and Python
5. An educator aims to teach **Mathematics by using educational robotics technology**. This path covers multiple mathematical concepts;
6. An educator aims to teach concepts in **Technology, Engineering and Mathematics**.

While providing those generic educational paths, we still consider it of utmost importance for teachers, pedagogues and researchers, while following the suggested curriculum paths, to tailor the activity plans to their context and thus design their own, separate curriculum.

The generic learning paths are a curriculum property, which will be further elaborated in the next months and will represent certain relationships between the activity plans contained in the curriculum.

Figure 1. Six educational paths of generic curricula presented as a metro map in which each point is an activity plan for and educational robotics workshop

To illustrate the concept, we could take for instance red line 3, as presented in Figure 1. The entire educational path, represented by the red line, consists of 37 hours of educational robotics content to cover all STEM domains complemented by concepts from domains such as business and art. The first “metro stop” where we “start the journey” is ES01 named “Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop. Within this workshops, students with no prior experience, related to the implementation of a technical project in a collaborative environment explore the fields of technology and engineering while constructing and programming a robotic vehicle and applying

mind-mapping to generate ideas on the application of robotics in various fields. The provoked students' interest and curiosity in technology are further developed within the second workshop ES02: Visualising Mathematics with Mathbot” where the students, who are already familiar with the basics of programming robot in Scratch, are exploring mathematical concepts, such as measuring angles, types of triangles, properties of a circle and proportions. In the next “metro stop”, UA01 named “An introduction to robotics - exploring planet ektonis” students have a chance to learn, further develop and practice concepts of science, technology and engineering while also using mathematics and art. At the last “metro stops” TW01 named “Robot-video elementary” and TW02 named “Robot-video advanced” the students are embarking on a hands-on learning experience in technology and engineering, while developing business skills and expressing their creativity through video and robotics. The same “metro line” could be taken the other way around, just by following the dashed red lines. As one can notice, the “metro map” illustrated in Figure 1, three of the five “metro stops” of the red line are also part of other proposed generic educational paths, serving different desired learning outcomes.

Powerful ideas

Our work in this dimension is in progress and focuses on what the central ideas are around which the activities evolve and how these are expressed in the robotic constructions. Powerful ideas are a central theoretical construct of constructionism and involve the use of knowledge in new ways where learners can establish personal epistemological connections with various domains of knowledge (Paret, 2000). Furthermore, analysing powerful ideas Bers (2008) describes them as domains of knowledge where many diverse topics or subjects co-exist and become explicit. Viewing activity plans from this lens poses the following challenges: a) powerful ideas might not imply a “progress” from one activity plan to another (in terms of student age, prerequisites etc) so we need to seek other connections that can be meaningful; b) not all activity plans are built around powerful ideas but they might have the potential to evolve in this direction. While traveling in the STEM metro line, students also develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, solve practical problems in teams, communicate with other teams to exchange ideas and tips in the social and actions domains.

Conclusion

We are confident that the presented approach for the organization of a generic curriculum will provide value to educators that are considering to apply educational robotics activities in their classrooms or would like to generate ideas on how to diversify their already applied approach. Furthermore, the work presented will attempt at visualizing the context and content of the educational robotics activities designed and developed within the project.

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